

**Complex Compounds of Platinum(II),
Palladium(II), Iridium(IV) and Rhodium(III)
with *p*-Phenylenebis(anisalideneimine)**

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In continuation of our report on the Cr^{III}, Fe^{III}, Mn^{III}, Co^{II} and Ni^{II} complexes with bis(benzylidene)benzidine having twentytwo-membered metal-lacyclic rings¹, this paper describes the synthesis of *N, N'*-*p*-phenylenebis(anisalideneimine) (hereafter, PBA) and its coordinating mode towards Pt^{II}, Pd^{II}, Ir^{IV} and Rh^{III} ions.

Experimental

The metal chlorides (Johnson Matthey) and *p*-phenylenediamine and anisaldehyde (B.D.H.) were used as such.

The Schiff base, PBA was synthesised by refluxing *p*-phenylenediamine (5.4 g, 0.05 mol) and anisaldehyde (12.1 ml, 0.1 mol) in 1 : 2 molar ratio in methanol (60 ml) for ~1.5 h under dry conditions using a calcium chloride tube. The solution was then concentrated at 65° on a hot-plate and left overnight for slow evaporation of the solvent to get the crude product which was recrystallised from MeOH and dried under reduced pressure.

The complexes were synthesised by stirring a solution containing equimolar amounts (0.004 mol) of the metal salt and the Schiff base in methanol (60 ml) at 45°. The complexes precipitated within 0.5 h. The resulting solids were washed several times with methanol and dried under reduced pressure.

The methods used for the characterisation were the same as described earlier².

Results and Discussion

Table 1 lists the stoichiometric data of the compounds. The ligand PBA and its metal complexes

were non-hygroscopic amorphous solids. But, unlike PBA, the complexes were soluble only in the polar solvents like DMSO. PBA had a sharp m.p. (198°) but the complexes decomposed to black powders in the temperature range 230–280°. The complexes were found to be 1 : 2 electrolytes².

Ir spectra : In the double bond region of the PBA spectrum, three strong bands appeared at 1 610, 1 580 and 1 515 cm⁻¹ due to $\nu_{C=N}$, $\nu_{C=C}$ ^{3,4} and δ_{C-H} ⁵ respectively. The $\nu_{C=N}$ vibrations appeared at lower frequencies, by 10–20 cm⁻¹, in the complexes. This lowering is attributed to a lowering of the C=N bond order as a result of the M–N bond formation¹. The complexes also exhibited medium intensity bands at 1 330–1 400 and 940–950 cm⁻¹ which are the characteristic deformation (δ_{O-CH_3}) and stretching (ν_{C-O}) modes of the coordinated methanol⁶. The new bands appearing near 300 cm⁻¹ region (Pt, 330 ; Pd, 310 ; Ir, 340 ; Rh, 330 cm⁻¹) are assigned to metal-chloride vibrations^{2,7}.

Thermal behaviour : The coordinated molecules of the solvent (MeOH) are removed in the temperature range 140–160°. The anisaldehyde parts of the complexes are lost, invariably, at lower temperature than the phenylenediamine moiety, emphasising thereby that only nitrogens of the Schiff base are involved in the coordination. Removal of the anisaldehyde parts in two steps, first methoxy (–OCH₃) and then =CHC₆H₅, may be due to involvement of the latter in the resonance system.

Electronic spectra : The electronic spectrum of the Pd^{II} complex is similar to other square-planar complexes with spectrochemically analogous ligands^{8,9}. The 23 255, 26 315, 29 411 and 35 087 cm⁻¹ bands are assignable to the ¹A_{1g}→³B_{1g}, →¹A_{2g}, →¹E_g and →¹B_{1g} transitions, respectively^{8,9,10}. The Racah repulsion parameters ($B=485$, $C=7B=3\ 395$ cm⁻¹), orbital energy differences ($\Delta_1=29\ 710$, $\Delta_2=39\ 233$, $\Delta_3=34\ 261$ cm⁻¹) and the angular overlap parameters (σ Pd–N=15 454, σ Pd–O=10 690, π -Pd– $\bar{L}$ =2 276 cm⁻¹) have been evaluated^{9,10}. The values of these parameters obviously indicate a stronger ligand field around Pd^{II} ion⁹. The magnitude of the π -Pd– $\bar{L}$ para-

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPLEXES

Compd.	Colour	Dec. temp. °C	Analysis : Found/(Calcd.)		
			N	M	OI
PBA	Pale gray	198	8.07 (8.18)	—	—
[Pt(PBA)Cl(MeOH)] ₂ Cl ₂	Reddish brown	230	4.89 (4.36)	31.94 (30.37)	12.2 (11.06)
[Pd(PBA)Cl(MeOH)] ₂ Cl ₂	Yellow	235	5.23 (5.06)	18.90 (19.21)	13.2 (12.89)
[Ir(PBA)Cl ₂ (MeOH)] ₂ Cl ₂	Dark brown	240	4.02 (3.78)	27.96 (27.04)	16.8 (19.14)
[Rh(PBA)Cl ₂ (MeOH)] ₂ Cl ₂	Dirty brown	280	4.51 (4.53)	18.11 (16.66)	19.70 (17.35)

meter shows considerable lateral overlapping of metal and ligand orbitals.

The observed magnetic moment of the Ir^{IV} complex (per metal atom) is 1.76 B.M. (calcd. 1.80 B.M.) which is nearer to the spin-only value of 1.73 B.M. The first band noted at 18 158 cm⁻¹ in the spectrum of this complex is consistent with the Laporte-forbidden ¹t_{1g}Cl_π → ²t_{2g} transition^{11,12}. This is further substantiated by the optical electronegativity of Cl⁻ calculated approximately as 2.9 for the above band using Xopt(M) as 2.3 for octahedral Ir^{IV} ion¹³. The other bands appearing at 23 948, 27 027, 35 087, 36 363 and 38 461 cm⁻¹ are attributed to the E_g⁴T_{1g}, E_g⁴T_{2g}, U_g³A_{2g}, U_g³T_{1g} and E_g^{1,2}T_{1g} states respectively¹⁴. The values of B, C, 10Dq and ζ have been evaluated as 577, 2 308, 42 260 and 4 096 cm⁻¹ respectively. The value of ζ (82% of the free ion value), is suggestive of a slight distortion from the octahedral geometry. This is understandably due to the unequal LF around the metal ion².

The 22 625, 25 641, 28 571 and 40 000 cm⁻¹ bands of the Rh^{III} complex are assignable to the ¹A_{1g} → ³T_{1g}, → ¹E_g, → ¹A_{2g} and → ¹T_{2g} transitions respectively¹⁵. Various LF parameters evaluated are B=714, Dq^{xy}=3 179, D_q^z=2 593, D_t=335, C=3 223, ρ_{xy}^z=19 174 and ρ_z^{xy}=15 657 cm⁻¹. Obviously, the in-plane ligand field is stronger than the axial one, i.e. the octahedron is distorted with axial elongation. It is concluded that the PBA(N₂) and MeOH(O₂) donor atoms are equatorially placed whereas the two chlorine ligands occupy the axial positions.

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Kinetics and Mechanism of Oxidation of Tellurium(IV) by Periodate in Perchloric Acid Medium

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ALTHOUGH the kinetics of oxidation of tellurium(IV) has been studied using a variety of oxidants¹, its mechanism is not yet well-understood. In order to get further insight into the mechanism, the present work reports the results of a detailed kinetic study of its oxidation by periodate in perchloric acid medium. The mechanism of this reaction seems to involve the transfer of an oxygen atom from periodate to tellurium(IV).

Experimental

A 0.1 mol dm⁻³ solution of Te^{IV} was prepared afresh by dissolving sodium tellurite (LR, B.D.H.) in water. A 0.1 mol dm⁻³ solution of Te^{VI} in 2.0 mol dm⁻³ perchloric acid was prepared from sodium tellurate (LR, B.D.H.). Aqueous solutions (0.1 mol dm⁻³) of periodate and iodate were prepared from sodium metaperiodate and potassium iodate (AnalaR) respectively. An approximately 8.0 mol dm⁻³ solution of sodium perchlorate was prepared by neutralising sodium carbonate (AnalaR) with 70% perchloric acid (Merck, pro analysi). All other chemicals used were of AR grade.

Kinetics of the reaction were studied at 60 ± 0.1° in 1.0 mol dm⁻³ perchloric acid medium keeping [Te^{IV}] in 10-fold excess over [periodate]. The reaction was monitored spectrophotometrically following the absorbance of periodate at 280 nm, where it has considerable absorption and all other ions involved in the reaction have negligible absorption. The rate constants were found to be reproducible within ± 5%.

Two- to four-fold excess of periodate was allowed to react with Te^{IV} at 60° in 1.0 mol dm⁻³ perchloric acid medium. After completion of the reaction, the concentration of the unreacted oxidant was determined spectrophotometrically. The stoichiometry of the reaction was found to be in the mole ratio of 1 : 1.